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THE ROLE OF METACOGNITION IN LEARNING

In this article we will try to address two fundamental questions. The first one is how to motivate foreign students studying the Ukrainian language to read in the classroom without prejudice to the content of the material. Second, what role do metacognitive processes play in teaching Ukrainian as a foreign language.

In the modern educational system, while teaching a foreign language, which is the Ukrainian language for foreign students, the emphasis is on a student-centered approach. This entails productive learning, not a dry transfer of knowledge to the student. The priority of productive learning is given by the student's independent learning activity. Currently, in connection with the pandemic in the world, which entailed global changes in the educational sphere, namely the transition to distance learning, independent work is given a huge place in the learning process. One of its main tasks is the formation of metacognitive skills, that is, the ability of students to independently plan their educational activities, do their own analysis of the work and independently evaluate it.

Studying the Ukrainian language, foreign students should be able to carry out speech activities in various situations. This means that they must learn to understand a foreign language by ear (listening); express thoughts by means of the target language (speaking); read, that is, understand a foreign language text, read both to oneself and aloud; to write, that is, to learn how to use the graphics and spelling of a foreign language when performing written assignments aimed at mastering reading and speaking, or to be able to express thoughts in writing.

Let's consider a type of speech activity like reading. Reading is included in the sphere of communicative and social activities of people, realized in the form of verbal mediated communication. Reading allows you to get the information contained in the written text. Reading is also a way of communicating through text. While reading is received and comprehension of written information. The purpose of reading is visual perception and understanding of information.

Let us dwell on the initial stage of teaching foreign students to read in Ukrainian. At the beginning of studying Ukrainian as a foreign language, the emphasis is on reading words and sentences aloud to form phonetic skills and abilities. In the future, reading to oneself is already allowed, since reading aloud should already be fluent with correct pronunciation, stress and intonation. At the

initial stage, the teaching of speaking and reading occurs simultaneously, which facilitates the goals and objectives set for reading. Since distance learning pays great attention to the independent work of students, reading, being one of the main types of communication activity, plays a role in the formation of metacognitive skills. Many foreign and some Ukrainian scientists are engaged in the study of metacognition. The concept of metacognition was introduced by John Flavell in 1976 and defined as a body of human knowledge about the main features of the cognitive sphere and its methods.

J. Flavell identified four components of metacognition: metacognitive knowledge, metacognitive experience, goals, and strategies.

A. Brown defines metacognition as knowledge about one's own knowledge. Also A. Brown points out that metacognitive processes allow you to regulate and control the learning process.

R. Kluwe, in turn, distinguishes two processes in the structure of metacognition that control and regulate cognitive processes.

Thus, when studying Ukrainian as a foreign language, metacognitive skills are very important. They allow foreign students to apply a generalized approach in order to see the generality of the mechanisms of the functioning of languages. To form students' information skills, the system of reading exercises includes types of tasks for information processing.

These tasks are of a semantic, cognitive, creative nature and are aimed both at the development of individual information skills and their integrative use. As a rule, students are offered pre-text assignments, assignments to check understanding and interpretation of what has been read, to compose their own oral (written) statements on a topic (problem, situation). In the exercises for mastering information skills, the nature of independent learning activity can consistently change from controlled, partially controlled by the teacher to independently controlled by students. These types of work are quite well-known and widespread in the practice of teaching a foreign language and are very relevant in the period of distance learning.

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